

The Students' Perception on Grade-Point Average (GPA) Score in Online Learning

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ABSTRACT

The purposes of this research were to identify the students' perception on GPA score in online learning in English Language Education study program of Universitas Nahdlatul Ulama Purwokerto, and to analyze the students' perception of the factors affecting English Language Education's batch 2019 of Universitas Nahdlatul Ulama Purwokerto GPA score. The subjects of this research were 20 students of English Language Education Study Program, academic year 2019/2020 that are active until the 4th semester, as proved by GPA score that not get zero score. The type of this research is qualitative research with descriptive approach. The instruments of data collection were documentation (in the form of GPA score) and interviews by Google Meet. Based on the result, there were increased and decreased score. According to the result of GPA score, there are several conditions. First, the students got GPA score and the ability increased. Second, the GPA score increased but the ability decreased. Lastly, the GPA score and the ability decreased. Meanwhile, the factors that affected students' GPA score were divided into two factors, internal and external. Internal factors included students' health, motivation, passion, talent and students' readiness. Meanwhile, the external factors included school environment and family motivation.

1. Introduction

The pandemic of COVID-19 gave many impacts for people in the world. The virus changed people's daily life, including teaching learning activity. The teaching and learning activity without directly face to face has been decided to prevent COVID-19 spreads in Indonesia by school cluster. Some problems appear when teaching and learning process through internet media applied in Indonesia. The students usually conduct the learning process at school with their teacher and friends, but now the activity should be done by several media through internet. Students should adapt with the new activity. Teaching and learning process with online learning used several applications as media. The popular applications

that used in online learning process especially at university are video conference such as WhatsApp, Zoom Meeting and Google Meet. They are the most popular application downloaded since the pandemic COVID-19, reported by databoks.katadata.co.id.

According to Mazda and Fikria (2021) Zoom Meeting and Google Meet are the applications that can be best solution in this pandemic era to prevent COVID-19 spread especially in education sector. The Ministry of Education and Culture decided about education system in pandemic era to do teaching and learning process by using those media. The changes of teaching and learning process affected students, especially for college students. They got very different activities to do and had to change their learning routines. The effect from online learning probably made impacts for the students. Some students may become more active and creative in the teaching and learning process, but the others may feel online learning is boring and make the students feel stress. Online learning may give impact also on students' academic score in their Grade-Point Average (GPA).

In this research, the researches wanted to identify the students' perception of their Grade-Point Average score in online learning and analyze the factors that affected the change of students' GPA based on the students' perception. Some researches about the impact of online learning in pandemic era for students were already conducted but most of them focus on one subject lesson score only. In this research, the researcher did not focus on one or two subject lessons only, but the researcher focused from the accumulation score of students or it is called Grade-Point Average (GPA).

The subject of this research was 20 students of English Language Education Study Program students academic year 2019/2020 at Universitas Nahdlatul Ulama Purwokerto. In this research, the researcher used descriptive qualitative research as a research method. The researcher used students' GPA in 4 semesters as documentation, and interview to collect the data.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Impact

Impact can be defined as consequence from a decision, policy, or a program. Impact is an evaluation step after formulating and implementing the policy or program. This definition supported by Elviani (2017) statement, she said that definition of impact is consequence result produce from policy or program. Impact can be used to be an evaluation or measurement about the success or fail the policy or program. In every policy or program there can giving impact for the participant. From the impact that produce by policy or program, the creator can decide what the next action after knowing the result are. The impact of a policy or a program can be a good impact or bad impact, depend on how the policy or program give advantage or disadvantage effect, and positive or negative effect for the participant.

2.1.1 Good Impact

Good is something that true, suitable with the norms in the society. Good is something that give positives aspect and advantages for someone and other. According to Webster's New Twentieth Century Dictionary (in Rahmawati 2015) good is something that produce the must feeling for satisfying, happiness, suitable and so on. In addition, according to Webster's World University Dictionary (in Rahmawati 2015) good is something that suitable

with the human wants. From the definition we can conclude that good is something that produce the feeling of satisfying, happiness, or so on that suitable with the human wants. Meanwhile, the definition of impact is consequence from a policy or program that apply. So, from the definition about good and impact, we can conclude that good impact is positive or advantage consequence from the policy or program that apply, that produce satisfying, happiness and so on that suitable with the norms in the society.

2.1.2 Bad Impact

The opposite from good, bad is something that not true, imperfect, terrible, unacceptable, break the rules, and unpleasant. Bad also gives negative aspect for someone and other. According to the Advanced Learner's Dictionary of Current English (in Rahmawati 2015) bad is contemptible, something which is contrary to current norms such us religious, law, social, and the other norms in the society. According to the definition we can conclude that bad is something that not true, unacceptable, something that break the rules of norms in the society, and bad also always gives negative aspect for people. Everything that bad always contra with good thing. After we know the definition from bad, we can combine the definition of bad and impact. If impact as consequence, so the definition of bad impact is consequence from the policy or program that contra with principles or norms that apply in the society.

2.2 Online Learning

The modernization of education in pandemic COVID-19 era makes teaching and learning process that normally do conventional at the classroom (face-to-face), nowadays it possible do in our home (through Online). In this modern era especially in pandemic era, teacher doesn't need to give the material by meet the students directly at the class. It happens as follow up from Ministry of Education and Culture decision about teaching and learning process in pandemic era. Teaching and learning process do at students or teacher home use internet technology.

Several popular applications that usually used as media in teaching and learning process at school especially at university are WhatsApp, Google Meet, Zoom Meeting, Google Classroom, Google form, and so on. With that applications, teacher and students are possible to communicate and sharing about the material with chat, voice note, or video call. The tools for online teaching and learning process are handphone, laptop, notebook, computer, and so on. Even though the teacher and the students are not in the same place, but modernization of technology especially in education make they can meet each other through the gadget screen.

Online learning is a form of distance education, which has long been a part of the American Education system, and it has become the largest sector of distance learning in the recent years, it is the opinion from Bartley & Golek (in Nguyen 20015). In Indonesia online learning conducted as activity to prevent the spreading of COVID-19. Harmani (2020) said that Online learning activity began on 16 March 2020. Meanwhile according to Bliuc, Goodyear & Ellis (in Dhawan 2020) purely online courses are course delivered entirely over the internet and hybrid or blended learning combines face-to-face classes, learning over the internet and learning supported by other technologies. From that definition before, we can conclude that online learning is a teaching and learning activity that conducted with no face-to-face

meeting but using the internet as media teaching and learning activity between teacher and students even though they are in difference place.

2.3 Factors of Learning Process

According to Slameto (2013:54) the factors that affect to student achievement in learning process divide into Internal and External Factor. Slameto said that internal factors included physical, psychology, and the factor of fatigue, meanwhile the external factors explained by Slameto included family, school, and society. Suryabrata (2012:233) also has opinion that the factors that affect to student achievement are internal factors included physiologies and psychologies, and the external factors are included social and non-social factor. The explanation about the factor will be explained as bellow:

2.3.1 Internal Factors

Internal factor is factor that makes human want to do an action and that factor come from the human itself. Internal factors that affect learning process of the students are all factors that giving impact in learning process that come from the human itself. According to Slameto (2013:54) and Suryabrata (2012:233) the internal factors that affects in learning process included body healthy, students' intelligence, students' motivation, students' passion, students' talent, and students' readiness. The explanation about internal factors that affect students learning process will be explained as bellow:

a. Healthy

A student who has a body healthy will produce good result in the learning process, and a person who has bad body healthy condition will produce the opposite result. Body healthy divides into physical healthy and phycology healthy. Two of them are important and give effect to get success in learning process. H. Djaali (2012) said that physical healthy is very important to increase learning achievement. It also happens when the students get problem in phycology healthy. The students that get conflict will affect student's achievement. It happens because they are not focus and interest with the learning process. Therefore, both physical healthy and phycology healthy are very important for student achievement in learning process.

b. Student Intelligence

Djaali (2012) said that intelligence has big effect for students' learning development. Djaali's opinions strengthened by Slameto (2013:56) the students or person who has high intelligence levels would be better in llearning achievement than those with low intelligence. Some of research said that intelligence is human ability that come from their genetic or from factor g, but some of them said that intelligence can created and developed by the human itself with hard study.

c. Students' Motivation

Motivation can make students more active and enthusiasm to learn, it can help the student to understand material in learning process. The same opinion delivered by Mohamadi (in Srivikaya 2019), he said that motivation can stimulate the students to complete an assignment, achieving a goal in learning, or giving spirit for learn. From that explanation we can conclude that motivation can produce energy that useful for academic work.

d. Student Passion

Student passion is about student desire to do something that they want, or they love, it usually come from student inside. Passion usually makes student having their big motivation to do something that they love. They will not feel stress or bored about something that become their passion. In the field of study student passion can influenced by intrinsic and extrinsic factor (Ismiyah & Liswatul 2012). The intrinsic factor based on Ismiyah and Liswatul (2012) included factors that come from the student-self such us students' feel, interest, need, and talent. While the extrinsic factors according to Ismiyah and Liswatul included factors that come from students outside such us student parents', teacher, friend, and teaching learning equipment.

e. Student Talent

Student's talent is probably different for each student, but it is possible also if student is same talent. According to Anggraini, Utami, Rahma (2020) talent can divide into academic talent and non-academic talent. The example of academic talent is the student talent in science, math, and the other subject relate with academic aspect. Usually, the students that have academic talent will be master a subject and motivated in every activity about the subject. The example of students' talent in non-academic talent such us playing music, dance, painting, teaching and so on. Student that has talent in non-academic talent usually can master the activity with full passion and motivation.

f. Student Readiness

The last is student readiness, it means the student's readiness to get information or insight from the teacher. The student's readiness is important part to determine the students get in teaching and learning process. According to Slameto (2015) learning readiness is the whole condition of the people that make them ready to give responds or answers in some situation. There are some factors that produce student learning readiness. There are 1) physiological equipment and growth, 2) Motivation of the students (Soemanto, in Idamayanti 2013). In this pandemic COVID-19 era, students' readiness is needed because the students should do a new activity in learning process. The students that usually use face to face in teaching and learning process but now should use online learning. The student should be ready for the new challenge in the recent day and prepare well for every challenges.

2.3.2 External Factor

Slameto (2013) and Suryabrata (2012) divide the external factor into three kinds, there are:

a. Family

According to Umar (in Latief 2014) family is the education center from the students. Family should be supporting system for the student in everything included in learning process. Family should understand what the student need and what the student wants to support the student in learning process. Family is the basic part in student education. The first teachers for student is their family. Family is first people that teach the student to speak, read, and sometimes write also. Family is also basic teacher to teach about norms and morals in student environment.

b. School

Syamsu and Nani (in Latief 2014) define school as systematic formal education institution that giving guidance, exercise, and information to build students potential in students intelektual, emosional, social, or phisycal, and the other. School environment included conducive class at school, the clean room, and school community (teacher, student, staff etc). Students need the clean and comfortable class for study, the equipment that need the good facilities, and good teacher. According to Slameto (in Latief 2014), factors that giving impact for students learning success at school are:

- 1) Learning Method
- 2) Curriculum
- 3) Teacher and students' relation
- 4) Students' relation
- 5) School discipline
- 6) Learning equipment
- 7) Time of school

c. Society

Society is a part of students' life included the students' friends, neighbors, and the students' activity in the society. Society is also about the student environment at their home, the example mountain, beach, or the other. Two of them are a unit called ecosystem. People or students and their society cannot be separated (Djamarah in Latief 2014). If the students are in good society like has smart or diligence friends so the student will be diligence also, if the students are in bad society like there are many lazy people, so the student will be bad also. The positive vibes in the society will create positive students also.

2.4. Grade Point Average (GPA)

Grading in education according to Yogendra and Andrew (2017) is the process of applying standardized measurements of varying levels of achievement in a course. GPA is the average of all final grades for courses within a program, weighted by the unit value of each of those courses (Yogendra and Andrew 2017). Based on the definition we can defined GPA or in Bahasa usually known as Indeks Prestasi Kumulatif (IPK) is one of measure of a student's academic abilities. GPA is an average credit unit that represent the quality of the teaching learning process accumulative each semester, or in short, can be interpreted as a measurement that express a student's quality in their academic.

GPA scores present in table that included students score in Letter, the weight of the score, and the Grade-Point Average result. The students' GPA score can be shown in the table below:

Table 2.1 Grade-Point Average score

Range	Letter	Weight	Predicate
86 – 100	A	4,00	Very Well
81 – 85	AB	3,50	More than good
71 – 80	B	3,00	Good

66 – 70	BC	2,50	More than enough
61 – 65	C	2,00	Enough
56 – 60	CD	1,50	Less than enough
51 – 55	D	1,00	Less
50 - <50	E	0,00	Fail

Grade Yogendra and Andrew (2017) defined student GPA is a calculation of the average of all student's total earned points divided by the units/SKS in the semesters that's already been through. Grade-Point Average is an important place in education as well as in the learning process. Scores become an index of child's future in this highly competitive world. Academic scores can be one of measurement of the educational process, is that process has the good result or bad result it can be measure by the student academic scores. Academic scores are one of instrument to measure the student knowledge, their talents, abilities, and competencies which are important part of developing career aspiration. In educational institutions, success is measured by academic performance or how well a student meets standards set by the educational institution. According to Tempo.co post in December 2021, three common the best honorary degree at university, there are:

1. Cumlaude

College students that got Grade-Point Average score in the range 3,51 - 3,79. They also should not get failed score or E in their units/SKS score.

2. Magna Cumlaude

Still same with Cumlaude degree to get this honorary degree, student should not get failed score or E in their units/SKS. The difference is the Grade-Point Average score in the range 3,80 – 3,99.

3. Summa Cumlaude

The higher honorary degree at university is Summa Cumlaude. Beside they should not get fail score or E in unit/SKS score, they should get 4,0 in their Grade-Point Average score.

2.5 Student's Point of view

In the recent day, we often heard about point of view. Point of view or perception is people direct response from a thing that people get by their sense, it can be from eye, ear, nose, feeling and so on. According to Shaleh (in Hilaliyah 2015) perception defined as process organized and mixed the data from our sense to develop, so we can understand about the situation un the environment and the situation of ourselves. In addition, Slameto (in Hilaliyah 2015) said that perception is a process from massage or information entry into the human brain. The massage or information entering human brain it can be through senses of sight, audience, taste, touch, and smell. The massage or information that entering the human brain will process become a perception or point of view. Perception or point of view can be difference between one and other. It happens because of the result of brain process may be difference each other based on the way to process the information.

So, from the definition we can conclude that perception is a process entrance the data from our sense such us mouth, eye, nose, taste, and touch and then the data interpret and organized become a new meaning. The example, when someone eats spicy food, they enter the data from their taste. After that, the brain interprets the taste and organized it in the memory and make a new meaning as perception that the spicy food is spicy. The other example, in this research the researcher wants to know about the student's perception about online learning. The student's perception created by students' activity in learning process. After students' activity entrance in the brain, the next one it will be interpreted and organized become a new meaning such us the online learning is interesting learning process or no for the student.

3. Research Methodology

In this research, the researcher used descriptive qualitative method. The reasons the researcher used descriptive qualitative because the focus of this research was about the impact of online learning for students's GPA and the reason of GPA's change viewed from the students' perception. The researcher wanted to identify and analyze the impact that probably happened because of online learning. To get the data, the researcher used student Grade-Point Average (GPA) score in 1st semester until 4th semester from English Language Education's students batch 2019/2020 as the guidance. The researcher asked the Grade-Point Average (GPA) from academic staff from Faculty Social, Economics, and Humanities of Universitas Nahdlatul Ulama Purwokerto.

The researchers' reason for choosing students from academic year 2019/2020 was because they recently experienced both, offline learning and online learning. They were students who did offline learning at Universitas Nahdlatul Ulama Purwokerto during 2019, and then pandemic made them did learning process through online learning in 2020. Therefore, the researcher could compare students' GPA score before Online Learning and after Online Learning. Techniques of collecting data that used by the researcher are documentation and interview.

3.1 Participants / Subject / Population and Sample

The population of this research were 28 students of English Language Teaching Department batch 2019 from Universitas Nahdlatul Ulama Purwokerto. Universitas Nahdlatul Ulama Purwokerto has 2 class in each major, there are A class and B class.

The sample of the data consisted of 20 English Language Teaching Department students' batch 2019 of Universitas Nahdlatul Ulama Purwokerto that divided into A and B class. According to the data from academic staff from Faculty Social, Economics, and Humanities of Universitas Nahdlatul Ulama Purwokerto, the English Language Teaching Department students' batch 2019 consisted of 19 A students and 9 B students. To determine the sample in this research, the researcher used purposive sampling to choose the sample in this research.

To get the sample, the researcher used student Grade-Point Average (GPA) score in 1st semester until 4th semester from English Language Teaching Department students' batch 2019 as the guidance. The researcher asked the Grade-Point Average (GPA) from academic Staff from faculty Social, Economics, and Humanities of Universitas Nahdlatul Ulama

Purwokerto. From the Grade-Point Average (GPA) score the researcher determined the sample from the GPA score those changes.

The researchers' reason for closed batch 2019 was because batch 2019 has recently experienced offline learning and online learning. The students' batch 2019 were students who did offline learning at Universitas Nahdlatul Ulama Purwokerto during a year in 2019, and then pandemic made them did learning process through online learning in 2020. Therefore, the researcher can compare students' GPA score before Online Learning and after Online Learning.

3.2 Instrument

The researcher used documentation in the form of Grade-Point Average (GPA) score and interview answer for instruments of research.

3.3 Data Analysis Procedure

Three steps that used to analyze the data are data reduction, data display, and conclusion drawing or verification (Sugiyono 2013, p. 245). The data analysis technique will explain as bellow:

1. Data reduction

Miles et al (2014) explained that data reduction is process of choosing, focusing, and summarizing the raw data from interview, observation, or documentation, or other qualitative data. In this part, the researcher summarized the data that collected by documentation and interview questions. In data document, the researcher reduced the data from Grade-Point Average score from English Language Teaching Department students' batch 2019 that got zero score (o score) in their Grade-Point Average score from 2nd, until 4th semesters. The student that got zero score (o score) mean the student was not active in teaching and learning process. The documentation taken from academic staff Universitas Nahdlatul Ulama Purwokerto. The interview data reduced from the interview answers that were not important enough for the research. The example of the data that not important enough for the research was about the student interaction with the researcher such us greeting.

2. Data display

After chosen the important data, and then made summary from the result of documentation, and interview in data reduction, the next step was data display. Miles and Huberman (2014) define data display as collection of information that gives the possibility getting the data conclusion. After getting data from students' Grade-Point Average as data documentation, and transcript answer from interview, the researcher displayed the data. In this step, the researcher displayed the data in the form of table. The purpose of data display was to help the researcher understand well about the data, and it helped the researcher to made conclusion from the research.

3. Conclusion drawing

The last step in triangulation technique of analysis the data is conclusion drawing. Miles and Huberman (2014) define conclusion drawing is a part of the whole research. Conclusion drawing is verification for the conclusions that appeared when do the research. In conclusion drawing step, the researcher showed the finding of the research based on the

data that the researcher got through Grade-Point Average score as documentation, and transcript answer from interview. In conclusion drawing, the researcher showed the result of the research finding about the impact of online learning for students Grade-Point Average score, and the factors from students' Grade-Point

4. Findings

4.1. Students' Grade-Point Average

Students	2 nd Semester	3 rd semester	Range	Note
1	3,88	3,92	0,04	Increase
2	3,50	3,53	0,03	Increase
3	3,65	3,67	0,02	Increase
4	2,98	2,74	-0,24	Decrease
5	3,25	3,28	0,03	Increase
6	3,05	3,03	-0,02	Decrease
7	3,65	3,50	-0,15	Decrease
8	2,63	2,85	0,22	Increase
9	3,60	3,53	-0,07	Decrease
10	2,55	2,59	0,04	Increase
11	2,70	2,75	0,05	Increase
12	2,80	2,85	0,05	Increase
13	2,88	2,93	0,05	Increase
14	2,80	2,93	0,13	Increase
15	2,75	2,77	0,02	Increase
16	2,98	3,00	0,02	Increase
17	2,90	2,97	0,07	Increase
18	2,70	2,75	0,05	Increase
19	3,70	3,75	0,05	Increase
20	3,75	3,82	0,07	Increase

To analyze more the GPA change, the researcher showed the result of students' GPA score in the graphic form as bellow:

Figure 2. Percentage of GPA score

From that information above, the researcher concluded that the result of students' GPA can be divided into two types, there are increased and decreased. It could be seen from the students' score changes. There were 16 students or 80% of student got positive result, it meant that the GPA score increased. Meanwhile 4 students or 20% of student got negative result that meant the GPA score decreased. The ranges of change of students' increase score is 0,02 – 0,1 point. Meanwhile the change range of students' decrease is 0,02 - 0,2 point.

4.2. Interview

The students' Grade-Point Average score is used to answer the first research question, and the researcher did the interview to answer the second research question. According to Sidiq and Choiri (2019), an interview is a process of communication interaction conducted by at least two people where the conversation refers to a predetermined. The interview section did by Google meet. The researcher invited the interviewees in a group of Google Meet. Interview questions in the interview section were 16 open-ended questions. Open-ended questions were chosen to get the clear answer and to explore their answer.

Based on the data interview from English Language Teaching Department Students' batch 2019, the researcher found that there were some internal factors and external factors that affecting English Language Teaching Department Students' GPA score changes. The internal factor included students' healthy condition, motivation, passion, talent, and students' readiness. Meanwhile the external factor that affecting the GPA of English Language Teaching Department students' batch 2019 were family motivation, school, and society environment.

5. Discussion

Based on the research has been conducted by documentation of GPA Scores and interview, the researcher found several points of students' perception as below:

5.1 Students' perception of GPA score in online learning

The students' perception of their GPA score in online learning divided into three types. First, the score and the ability increased. Second, the score increased but the ability was decreased. Lastly, the score and the ability was decreased.

a. GPA score and ability increased

From the documentation and interview result, a student argued that his GPA score and the ability increased. It happened because he still maximized the learning process even though the learning process conducted in online learning. Even though there were some negative effects from the online learning for the students, there was still positive effect appear for some students. According to Argaheni (2020) even though online learning sometimes confusing the students, created passive student, less useful information that given, made students stress, but online learning can increase student literacy skill for them who wants to read. Hunain was one of the students that still wanted to study and search the material by himself. It could be a way to increase his ability in English even though the teaching and learning process conducted by online learning.

b. The GPA score increased but ability decreased

The most opinion that delivered by the students was about the GPA score that increased but the English ability was decreased. It happened because most of the students used Google Translate in the learning process. They used Google Translate when they wanted to read, write text even before they were going to speak up. According to Fitriani et al (2021) translators have positive aspects that can be used as the media to translate, as media to learn about pronunciation, and made efficient to translate words. However, translator also has the negative aspect such as google translate made dependency of the students, then the students lazy to open the manual dictionary and look for other reference, and it can decrease the student's ability in writing because sometimes the structure is wrong. Google translate also can decrease the students' ability in memorizing an English word because the student got the sentence in the instant form.

c. GPA Score and ability decreased.

The other opinion is the GPA score and the ability was both decreased. It happened because they were not ready enough in the learning process through online learning. Argaheni (2020) already argued that online learning made the students felt confused in learning process that usually conducted in several applications such as WhatsApp, Zoom Meeting, Google Meet, Google classroom and the other. The students also became passive students because they chose to read only and not respond to the lecturer. The other reason was the students feeling stress with the pandemic era and many assignments that given by the lecturer.

5.2 Factors Affecting students' Grade-Point Average score

From the research result of interview, the researcher found that there were two factors that affecting students' GPA. There are internal factors and external factors. The researcher discussed the research findings as bellow:

5.2.1 Internal factors

Internal factors are factors that affect the human want to do an action and that factors come from the human itself. In this research, the researcher found some of internal factors

that affect students GPA score such as students' passion, talent, students' readiness, students' motivation, healthy body.

1) Students' Passion

Student passion is about student's desire to do something that they want, or they love, it usually comes from student inside. According to Covey (cited in Monica and Prasetya 2015) passion is strong desire, strong belief, and encouragement that makes a person disciplined to achieve his dream. From the students' answers, the researcher indicated that they did not make English subject as their passion. From the data, there are only 4 students or 20% of the student that chose English as their favorite subject. 16 students or 80% of them chose the other subjects such as Aswaja, Kewirausahaan, even Bahasa Indonesia. It indicated that English is not their passion.

Even though English was not their passion, but they still tried to learn and study about English language with their own way. From the data, they are 11 students or 55% of the students studied independently. Some of them were listening to English songs, watching an English movie, or watching an English content on YouTube to increase their English skill. From the data, the researcher indicated that English is not their passion, but they are still listening to English song, watching English movie and so on as their hobby.

2) Students' Talent

From 20 students as interviewee, there are 9 students or 45% of students that learning English at Elementary School, and 11 students or 55% of the students learning English at their Junior High School. Next is interview question number 4 about the students' skill or students' talent also. From the total interviewees, 99% of students or 19 students said that their skill were still weak. Meanwhile only one student said that his skill is quite good enough. From the interviewees' answer, the researcher indicated that English is not their talent. From the interviewees' answer the researcher indicated that they were learning English because it was a compulsory subject at school, and not about their talent. According to Anggraini Utami and Rahma (2020), the characteristic of student talent is the field of student talent will be dominant than the other field.

3) Students' readiness

From the total interviewees there were only 3 students who preferred to online learning. The most votes preferred to offline learning or face-to-face teaching. There were 16 students or 80% of students choosing offline learning. Meanwhile 1 student or 0,5% of students chose both. From the interviewees' answers the researcher indicated that they were not ready enough to do online learning. According to Slameto (2010 p. 113) learning readiness is the whole condition of the people that make them ready to give responds or answers in some situation. The indication appeared because the students could not accept the condition yet so it made them not ready to give good responds in teaching and learning process.

4) Students' Motivation

According to Mohamadi (in Srivikaya 2019), he said that motivation can stimulate the students to complete an assignment, achieve a goal in learning, or give spirit for learning. From the students' answers, almost all the students did their homework or assignment. There are 16 students or 80% of the students did their homework, and 3 students or 20% students did not do their homework. The students argued that homework or assignments

gave them an advantage. There are 8 students or 40% of students argued that homework or assignment increase their responsibility and there were 12 students or 60% of students argue dthat homework or assignment as practice media for learning about the subject. From that data, the researcher indicated that the students were motivated to do their homework because they realized that homework gives them advantages.

5) Students' Health

Based on the data, all students agreed that healthy body is important factor that affecting students learning achievement. According to Slameto (2013) and Suryabrata (2015) body health is divided into physical healthy and phycology healthy. They are important for the student, especially for learning achievement. According to the students, the healthiest case that appeared during online learning was about the student's mental health. The students usually felt stress about the assignment or the homework that was given by the lecture. Stress made the students not focus to accept the material that was given by the lecturer. They also sometimes felt not interested in the material that was given by the lecturer.

5.2.2 External Factors

According to Slameto (2013) there are three factor external that affect students' learning achievement. There are family, school, and society environment.

1) Family environment

Based on the students' answers, all the students agreed that family motivation is important for students' learning achievement and it worked for students GPA score. Based on the data, the researcher indicated that the family's motivation is one of factors that affecting students GPA. It is suitable with Slameto (2013) and Suryabrata (2012)'s statement that family is one of external factors in learning achievement. Family motivation made the student aware about their GPA as students' measurement in learning process.

2) School Environment

Based on the data, all the students agreed that their lecturers have the ability in teaching and learning process through online learning. From 20 English Language Education Study Program students or 100% agreed that the lecturer can adapt and improve their ability in teaching and learning process during online learning. From the data, the researcher indicated that the school environment, especially lecturers' ability in Universitas Nahdlatul Ulama Purwokerto is good enough. According to Supriyadi (in WD Anggraini 2016) if the teacher or lecturer used teaching method that is suitable with the students' needs, so the opportunity to obtain learning outcomes that are in accordance with student expectation will be greater.

3) Society environment

According to Slameto (2013) and Suryabrata (2012) social environment is one of external factors that supports learning achievement. Based on the data, there is only 7 students or 35% of the students argued that society environment gave them impact in GPA score. It happened because they cannot study at noisy situation. The other reason was the students getting bad internet connection in their home because some of them lived in rural area. Therefore, they felt difficult to follow the material, joined meeting or sent and uploaded an assignment. Even though there were 13 students or 65% students argued that society environment did not give them impact in GPA score change. From the data, the researcher

indicated that society environment only giving impact for the students who got bad internet connection in their environment or in their village.

6. Conclusion

Based on the research, the students' GPA score of English Language Education Study program (Academic Year 2019/2020) experienced increased and decreased. It can be seen from student GPA score that 80% of the students or 16 students got increased score and 4 students or 20% of the students got decreased score. The students' perception on their GPA divided into three types. There are GPA score and the ability increased, the GPA score increased but the ability was decreased, and the GPA score and the ability was decreased.

The factors that affecting the students' GPA score change were internal factor (students' healthy, passion, talent, motivation, and readiness) and external factor (students' family motivation, school environment and society).

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